

Feedstock composition and process parameter selection for Indian hydrocrackers

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Hydrocracking in a high pressure batch reactor has been studied to find out a suitable feedstock and the corresponding process conditions, viz. temperature, total pressure, residence time and hydrogen initial pressure which fits the Indian hydrocrackers, aiming to middle distillate.

Hydrocracking and Fluid catalytic cracking (FCC) are the most popular upgradation techniques. Although, hydrocracking is more complex as compared to FCC, yet it is the ultimate solution for the zero heavy-end based refinery as well as for the production of on-grade products contributing to almost pollution-free atmosphere. In India, FCC is dominating the petroleum industry because of lower expense and of available state-of-the-art technology. It is, therefore, a great challenge to make hydrocracking economically comparable to FCC by developing state-of-the-art technology considering particularly the feedstock availability, product demand and Indian economy. The present investigation, is an attempt in this area of research aiming towards Indian requirements.

The entire study aims to hydrocrack vacuum gas oil (VGO) to middle distillate (MD) selectively. For this purpose, two vacuum gas oils, one paraffinic (from indigenous source) and the other naphthenic (from Middle-East source) in nature, were chosen as the feedstock (Table 1). Molecular sieve 13X with nickel loading was used as the catalyst (Ni, 2.5 wt%; sp. surface area, 289.25 m² g⁻¹; total pore volume, 0.769 ml g⁻¹; surface acidity, 0.90 mg g⁻¹). Study of the effect of the process parameters on conversion, MD selectivity and product quality was done as follows : temp., = 598–748 K; total pressure, 3.4–8.16 Mpa; residence time, 7–60 min; initial pressure of H₂, 3.4–6.31

MPa, and from this, suitable feedstock for Indian hydrocrackers is suggested alongwith a set of optimum process conditions which will help Indian refiners to meet the growing demand of MD¹.

Results and Discussion

Effect of temperature : Table 2 shows that highest conversion and highest yield of MD are obtained for VGO_{II}, i.e. for naphthenic-based feedstock at 698 K. The quality of the product is also satisfactory. The trend (i.e. the effect of temperature on yield and MD selectivity), however, is almost same for both the paraffinic and naphthenic feedstocks but the difference lies in the workable temperature range. The naphthenic feeds can be operated at quite low temperature range (648–698 K) as compared to paraffinic one, which is due to lower reactivity of the paraffins. As product composition is concerned, the change is very sharp for naphthenic one which also reveals that the effect of temperature is more pronounced in case of naphthenic feed.

Effect of total pressure : The study reveals that the yield of liquid product as well as of MD is higher for naphthenic feedstock (Table 3) This may be due to the fact that pressure variation is not favourable for the cracking of paraffins via olefin intermediate. Further, increase in total pressure increases the aromatic content of the hydrocracked product for naphthenic feed, which is probably due to various secondary reactions occurring predominantly as pressure is increased thus yielding liquid product.

Effect of residence time : The effect of residence time shows that residence time has almost the same effect on both the feedstocks under consideration, although differing in the extent, as yield of MD is concerned (Table 4). The yield of MD increases at first, passes through a maxima (at 15 min) and then decreases, which is due to the onset of secondary reactions – this is true for both the feedstocks. Thus optimum residence time found for both the feed is 15 min, but VGO_{II} yielding more liquid product and more MD as com-

Table 1. Characteristics of feedstocks

Parameter	VGO _I	VGO _{II}
Characterization factor	12.2	11.05
Type	Paraffinic	Naphthenic
Boiling range, K	623–753	623–753
Density (293 K), g dm ⁻³	0.875	0.878
Sulfur, wt%	0.24	1.6
Ramsbottom C-residue, wt%	0.6	0.39
% Aromatics	27	30
Pour point, K	318	271

Table 2. Effect of temperatureFeed Catalyst ratio = 10 : 1, residence time = 15 min, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.4 Mpa (total pressure)

Parameter	VGO _I				VGO _{II}			
	648	698	723	748	648	698	723	748 K
(a) Yield, wt% of feed								
Liquid product	10	62.8	63.2	53.6	84.8	85.6	74.0	60.0
MD (423–573 K)	–	11.3	37.9	26.6	38.2	49.4	39.0	35.6
(b) % Aromatics in product	–	33	34	29	38	37	50	40
(c) Pour point of MD, K	–	281	269	261	–	258	259	259

Table 3. Effect of total pressureFeed Catalyst ratio = 10 : 1, residence time = 15 min, temp = 723 K for VGO_I and 698 K for VGO_{II}, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.4 Mpa

Parameter	VGO _I				VGO _{II}			
	3.4	5.44	6.8	8.16	3.4	5.44	6.8	8.16 Mpa
(a) Yield, wt% of feed								
Liquid product	63.2	58.8	64.0	66.4	85.6	68.0	71.8	55.2
MD (423–573 K)	37.9	40.7	24.1	33.4	49.4	60.5	62.4	50.2
(b) % Aromatics in product	34	22	28	32	37	43	44	50
(c) Pour point of MD, K	269	260	261	265	258	248	248	250

Table 4. Effect of residence timeFeed Catalyst ratio = 10 : 1, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.4 Mpa, temp and total pressure = 723 K and 5.44 Mpa (VGO_I), 698 K and 6.8 Mpa (VGO_{II})

Parameter	VGO _I				VGO _{II}			
	7	15	30	60	7	15	30	60 min
(a) Yield, wt% of feed								
Liquid product	59.2	64.0	68.0	63.2	76.8	72.0	66.0	72.0
MD (423–573 K)	27.7	40.7	36.7	30.0	43.6	62.4	37.3	43.5
(b) % Aromatics in product	27	22	30	34	34	44	40	42
(c) Pour point of MD, K	263	260	259	262	259	248	251	249

Table 5. Effect of initial pressure of H₂Feed Catalyst ratio = 10 : 1, residence time = 15 min, temp and total pressure = 723 K and 5.44 Mpa (VGO_I), 698 K and 6.8 Mpa (VGO_{II})

Parameter	VGO _I			VGO _{II}		
	3.4	4.24	4.93	3.4	4.24	4.93 Mpa
(a) Yield, wt% of feed						
Liquid product	64.0	58.0	61.6	72.0	70.0	74.8
MD (423–573 K)	40.7	26.6	29.9	62.4	39.4	48.2
(b) % Aromatics in product	22	32	30	44	55	50
(c) Pour point of MD, K	260	259	260	248	255	253

pared to VGO_I. It can, therefore, be said that secondary reaction in case of naphthenic feed is more affected by pressure variation (as found in b) and not by residence time variation; the almost constant value of aromatic content of the hydrocrackate in the range 15–60 min also supports this.

Effect of initial pressure of hydrogen : The results (Table 5) of the effect of initial pressure of hydrogen reveal that the increase in initial pressure of hydrogen decreases the MD yield drastically for both the feeds, which again increases to some extent as pressure is increased further, and the effect is

more pronounced in case of VGO_{II}. It is thus clear that maximum MD yield can be achieved at low initial pressure of hydrogen, which is 3.4 Mpa for the feeds studied. Therefore, increase in initial pressure of hydrogen has no favorable effect on MD yield, particularly when using nickel as the hydrogenating-dehydrogenating component; since, nickel adsorbs hydrogen but does not allow it to diffuse efficiently, thus availability of hydrogen is not adequate (although initial pressure of hydrogen is increased) to promote hydrocracking reactions leading to MD.

It can, therefore, be concluded that naphthenic vacuum gas oil is more suitable to hydrocrack to meet the indigenous demand of MD using nickel-based zeolite catalysts with consequent saving in heat energy and hydrogen requirement.

Experimental

The laboratory model of high-pressure batch reactor used and experimental setup are described elsewhere². The reactor charged with requisite amount of feed and catalyst was sealed properly. H₂ and/or N₂ was then introduced upto the required initial pressure. The reactor was heated to the desired temperature when rocking started and continued until the residence time under study was completed. Hot release of the gas and vapour was then accomplished through a condenser, collector and gas-meter assembly. The liquid

product collected was fractionated into different fractions in a standard ASTM apparatus³ and the required properties were tested.

The catalyst preparation involved only metal impregnation on the pre-formed molecular sieve 13X support. It was done in the most conventional way of ion-exchanging – first with ammonium ion and then with the nickel ion. The process is described in details elsewhere⁴.

References

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